

AN AHP (ANALYTIC HIERARCHY PROCESS)/FCE (FUZZY COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION)-BASED MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION APPROACH FOR LOOKING FOR THE BEST ALL TIME COLLEGE COACHES

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Abstract

In this paper the AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) and the FCE (Fuzzy Comprehensive Evaluation) are applied to find the best coaches from different sports and to rank these great coaches.

First, we screen coaches' information using three screening criteria. We rank the screened coaches preliminarily by means of analytic hierarchy process (AHP). Second, we rank them by fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method(FCE), and we determined the top5 coaches on basketball, football and hockey. Third, we use the Topsis method to test the accuracy and reasonableness of the model, modify the model and then reorder the original results to inspect the consistency of the results of the two models. Finally, we take some other factors into account to optimize our model, which includes on the influence of time line horizon and genders.

KEYWORDS

Analytic hierarchy process(AHP), Fuzzy comprehensive evaluation(FCE), Topsis method, Best coach.

1. INTRODUCTION

The analytic hierarchy process (AHP)[1-3] is a structured technique for organizing and analyzing complex situation. It is based on mathematics and psychology. Rather than prescribe a “correct” decision, the AHP helps decision makers find one that best suits their goal and their understanding of the problem. It provides a comprehensive and rational framework for structuring a decision problem, for representing and quantifying its elements, for relating those elements to overall goals, and for evaluating alternative solutions.

Fuzzy Comprehensive Evaluation Method[4] is a comprehensive evaluation method based on fuzzy mathematics. The comprehensive evaluation method is based on the theory of fuzzy mathematics degree of membership of the qualitative evaluation into quantitative evaluation, which apply fuzzy mathematics subject into many factors or objects to make an overall assessment. It has a clear result, as well as some systematic and strong features, which can be a

good way to solve than the vague, difficult to quantify the problem, suitable for solving the problem of non-deterministic.

The TOPSIS method can also be used to deal with multi- criteria decision making (MCDM) problem. Several extensions of this method have been suggested. The simplest extension is to change a fuzzy MCDM problem into a crisp one by applying the defuzzification method [5]. However, this approach can cause some information lost and gives only a crisp point estimate for the relative closeness of each criteria. Although the extension gives a fuzzy relative closeness for each criteria, it was determined that the supports of the derived fuzzy relative closeness are over exaggerated[6]. The extension principle is therefore not advisable either. To overcome these shortcomings, the TOPSIS method and the extension principle were combined to solve fuzzy MCDM problems.

In the 20th century, a great number of top coaches were born in American colleges and many sports fancier wanted to rank these great coaches, but it is not an easy job because the evaluation of coaches is determined by many factors.[7] This paper focus on coming up with a strategy on what will be both the most efficient and accurate way to find the best coaches. All information of candidate coaches is obtained from [8-11]. The rest of this paper is organized as follows: in Section 2, we screen coaches' information using three screening criterions. Section 3 to section 6 presents four parts of our multi-criteria decision approach in detail. Conclusions are provided in the last Section.

2. SCREENING TARGET INFORMATION

We first screen coaches' information obtained by three initial screening criterions:

- (1) Teaching periods within the scope of the last century. If the coaches can span a century, we have special treatment.
- (2) Teach for 10 years or more. The longer a coach works for, the richer experience is and the better he has profound understanding of specific sports, which helps him become a good coach.
- (3) The races during teaching time won more than 50%. Ability to command games is the necessary skill for excellent coaches, playing a key role in the victory.

After screening under the above conditions, we left 80 coaches in each three groups to evaluate.

3. AHP

First, the problem can be divided into three levels. The top is the goal layer, namely the need to choose a college coach; the bottom is object layer; the middle layer is the criterion layer. The 11 indexes are expressed as $P_i = \{\text{Coaching time, game, win, Personal honors, win\%, Training method, management, Game style, social influence, individual quality, social appraisal}\}$. Hierarchical structure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure. 1 Hierarchical structure diagram

Then we list the second layer, third layer, the fourth layer criteria comparison matrix layer and make normalization processing for the matrix. Random consistency ratio CR can be calculated by:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (1)$$

where CI denotes consistency degree, expressed by (2), RI denotes Average random consistency index.

$$CI = \frac{\lambda - n}{n - 1} \quad (2)$$

where λ is the maximum eigenvalue of the comparison matrix, n is the number of the matrix. Table 1 shows the related importance between factor c_i and c_j .

Table 1. The relative importance

The relative importance a_{ij} between C_i and $C_j, i, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$	Degree
Equally important	1
Generally more important	3
Far more important	5
More important at the second highest degree	7
More important at the highest degree	9
For compromises between the above	2, 4, 6, 8
In comparing elements i and j , if i is 3 compared to j , then j is $1/3$ compared to i	Reciprocals of above

Consistency index can be obtained:

Second layer: Best Coach:

	Overall	Career	Personality
Overall	1.00	3.00	4.00
Career	0.33	1.00	2.00
Personality	0.25	0.50	1.00

Weight matrix $W_1 = [0.6232, 0.2395, 0.1373]$, $CR_1 = 0.0176 < 0.1$.

Third layer: Overall: $W_2 = [0.6232, 0.2395, 0.1373]$, $CR_2 = 0.0176 < 0.1$.

Career: $W_3 = [0.6000, 0.2000, 0.2000]$, $CR_3 = 0.0000 < 0.1$.

Personality: $W_4 = [0.6000, 0.2000, 0.2000]$, $CR_4 = 0.0000 < 0.1$.

Fourth layer: Team: $W_5 = [0.2000, 0.6000, 0.2000]$, $CR_5 = 0.0000 < 0.1$.

Personal: $W_6 = [0.8000, 0.2000]$, $CR_6 = 0.0000 < 0.1$.

Table 2. The weight of vector elements

The first level (weight)	The second level (weight)	The third level (weight)	The fourth level (weight)
Best Coach (1.0000)	Honor (0.6232)	Team (0.4155)	Game (0.0831)
			Win (0.2493)
			Win% (0.0831)
		Personal (0.2077)	Personal honors (0.1662)
			Coaching time (0.0415)
			Career (0.2395)
	Management (0.0479)		
	Game style (0.0479)		
	Personality (0.1373)	Social influence (0.0824)	
		Individual quality (0.0275)	
		Social appraisal (0.0275)	

After completing the analysis of all the evaluation elements needed, we are able to analyze the degree of excellence of each coach in accordance with the scores on each weight of vector element. However, some information also cannot be quantified, so we will solve this problem by using FCE method.

4. FCE

4.1. FCE Algorithm

Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ characterize the object being evaluated m kind of evaluation factors (evaluation) where: m is the number of evaluation factors, a specific indicator system is determined.

Let $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the set of evaluation which reflects the various levels of the evaluation object, where v_j represents the first evaluation of the results of the $j, j=1, 2, \dots, n$. n is the total number of the evaluation results that are usually divided into 3 to 5 grades.

Let $A = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m)$ be the weight (weight) distribution of fuzzy vector, where $a_i > 0, \sum a_i = 1$. A reflects the importance of each factor. Use univariate fuzzy evaluation to establish the fuzzy relationship matrix R .

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11} & \cdots & r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1} & \cdots & r_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$$

where r_{ij} represents a factor evaluated from the perspective of membership of u_i level of fuzzy subsets v_j . Synthesizing fuzzy weight vector A and fuzzy relationship matrix R , we obtain the results of the evaluation object vector B .

$$B = A \circ R = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m) \begin{pmatrix} r_{11} & \cdots & r_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{m1} & \cdots & r_{mn} \end{pmatrix} = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n) \quad (3)$$

4.2. Solving steps

The Abstract section begins with the word, “Abstract” in 13 pt. Times New Roman, bold italics, “Small Caps” font with a 6pt. spacing following. The abstract must not exceed 150 words in length in 10 pt. Times New Roman italics. The text must be fully justified, with a 12 pt. paragraph spacing following the last line.

- (1) Determine the set of factors to be evaluated

According to the established model system, we determine the set of objects factor which needs to be evaluated: $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\} = \{\text{training method, management, game style, social influence, individual quality, social appraisal}\}$.

- (2) Determine the set of evaluation object comment

According to the degree of influence of our target, we set up a grade evaluation set as follows:

$$V = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4\} = \{\text{one (100 '), two (80'), three (60 '), four (40')}\}$$

- (3) Determine the weight vectors

In the previous section, we've got the weight of the object to be evaluated: $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\} = \{0.1437, 0.0479, 0.0479, 0.0824, 0.0275, 0.0275\}$.

- (4) Determine the evaluation matrix

We screened eighty soccer coaches, which were carried out to become the best coach in the level of evaluation. Tab. 3 shows the evaluation matrix of Eddie Robinson.

Table 3. The evaluation matrix

Grade (Score)	Level one (100')	Level two (80')	Level three (60')	Level four (40')
training method	0.3	0.35	0.2	0.15
management	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.1
Game style	0.15	0.3	0.5	0.05
social influence	0.8	0.1	0.05	0.05
individual quality	0.4	0.5	0.07	0.03
social appraisal	0.7	0.2	0.08	0.02

(5) Fuzzy comprehensive evaluation

That fuzzy comprehensive evaluation model: $B = A \circ R$. Here, fuzzy composite operator is taken as an ordinary matrix multiplication algorithm.

$$c(i) = \sum_{j=1}^j r(i)(j) * v(j)$$

$$C = (c(1), c(2), c(3) \dots c(i))$$

$$B = C * R = (10.9212, 3.5466, 3.4009, 7.6632, 2.3485, 2.519) \tag{4}$$

When Eddie Robinson is elected as the best coach, the scores of management, game style, social influence, individual quality, social appraisal are 10.9212, 3.5446, 3.4009, 7.6632, 2.3485, 2.519.

With the help of the coaches' scores on these programs based on AHP, we can score for all

coaches and rank them. So the overall score $S = \sum_{i=1}^{11} d(i) * a(i)$. In following, table 4 shows the top twenty football coaches and their scores.

Table 4. Rank of the top 20 football coaches

Rank	Coach	Coaching time	Game	Win	Personal honors	Wink	training method	manag ement	Game style	social influence	indiv idual quali ty	social appraisal	Score
1	Eddie Robinson	4.15	8.31	24.87	14.96	5.88	10.92	3.55	3.40	7.66	2.35	2.52	88.56
2	Bear Bryant	2.77	6.01	19.69	16.62	6.48	10.74	7.55	2.50	10.73	1.35	2.41	86.84
3	Joe Paterno	3.35	7.75	24.93	12.00	6.22	11.46	2.45	3.25	6.96	3.95	2.92	85.24
4	Bobby Bowden	2.91	6.85	21.76	8.77	6.15	9.48	3.44	2.80	6.46	2.79	2.44	73.85
5	Tom Osborne	1.82	4.34	15.54	14.77	6.95	10.10	2.85	3.35	7.48	2.17	2.31	71.77
6	Woody Hayes	2.04	3.90	12.50	12.47	6.32	10.05	2.79	2.85	7.31	1.94	2.03	65.57
7	Pop Warner	3.06	6.30	18.96	4.16	6.09	10.29	2.74	3.14	7.75	1.99	2.43	65.52
8	Do Schebechler	1.97	4.34	14.26	12.93	6.44	9.06	1.85	2.04	5.21	1.46	1.78	61.33
9	Hick Saban	1.31	3.22	10.36	13.39	6.22	9.78	2.55	2.99	6.71	1.88	2.36	60.78
10	LaVell Edwards	2.11	5.10	15.67	11.08	5.95	8.12	2.32	2.11	5.31	0.97	1.54	60.27
11	Bob Neyland	1.53	3.05	10.55	7.39	6.89	8.99	4.05	3.07	6.77	3.01	4.24	59.53
12	Barry Switzer	1.17	2.69	9.57	8.31	6.96	8.73	3.97	3.02	6.47	2.99	4.18	58.04
13	Vince Dooley	1.82	4.07	12.25	11.08	5.94	8.51	2.79	2.01	4.99	0.44	3.12	57.03
14	Darrell Royal	1.68	3.52	11.22	10.16	6.22	8.59	2.80	2.05	5.08	1.52	3.15	55.99
15	Bob Stoops	1.09	2.81	9.75	8.31	6.68	9.61	3.02	3.06	5.25	2.92	3.20	55.71
16	Howard Jones	2.04	3.80	11.46	6.46	6.08	9.50	2.39	2.70	5.34	2.62	2.63	55.02
17	John Vaught	1.82	3.72	11.58	8.77	6.19	9.29	1.72	2.34	4.96	2.15	1.83	54.36
18	Steve Spurrier	1.75	4.24	13.35	8.31	6.09	8.56	1.25	2.25	4.12	1.44	1.59	52.96
19	Dan McCugin	2.18	3.83	12.01	4.62	6.33	9.34	1.74	2.35	4.99	2.16	1.88	51.43
20	Fielding Yost	1.82	2.88	10.06	7.39	6.92	7.66	1.10	2.17	3.86	1.25	1.02	46.13

We can use the same method to get the rank on other sports. In order to save space, we leave out the ranks of basketball and hockey coaches.

5. MODEL CHECKING

Topsis method has no special request for the sample, and it is easy to apply to different problems. Its basic idea includes: normalization of the original data matrix, find the best and the worst in the limited program to constitute a space, so that we can get the distance (Euclidean distance) from the point to the optimal solution. Now, we use the football coaches as test samples.

(1) Evaluate polarity, give the polarity matrix

$$x_{i1}^* = 1 / x_{i1}^* \quad (5)$$

Table 5. The polarity matrix

Rank	Coach	Coaching time	Game	Win	Personal honors	Win%	training method	management	Game style	social influence	individual quality	social appraisal
1.00	Eddie Robinson	4.15	8.31	24.87	14.96	5.88	10.92	3.55	3.40	7.66	2.35	2.52
2.00	Bear Bryant	2.77	6.01	19.69	16.62	6.48	10.74	7.55	2.50	10.73	1.35	2.41
3.00	Joe Paterno	3.35	7.75	24.93	12.00	6.22	11.46	2.45	3.25	6.96	3.95	2.92
4.00	Bobby Bowden	2.91	6.85	21.76	8.77	6.15	9.48	3.44	2.80	6.46	2.79	2.44
5.00	Tom Osborne	1.82	4.34	15.54	14.77	6.95	10.19	2.85	3.35	7.48	2.17	2.31

Table 6. The consistency matrix

Rank	Coach	Coaching time	Game	Win	Personal honors	Win%	training method	management	Game style	social influence	individual quality	social appraisal
1	Eddie Robinson	0.241	0.12	0.04	0.067	0.17	0.092	0.282	0.294	0.13	0.426	0.397
2	Bear Bryant	0.361	0.167	0.051	0.06	0.154	0.093	0.133	0.4	0.093	0.741	0.415
3	Joe Paterno	0.299	0.129	0.04	0.083	0.161	0.087	0.408	0.307	0.144	0.253	0.343
4	Bobby Bowden	0.343	0.146	0.046	0.114	0.163	0.106	0.291	0.357	0.155	0.358	0.41
5	Tom Osborne	0.549	0.23	0.064	0.068	0.144	0.098	0.351	0.298	0.134	0.46	0.433

(2) Normalization of the data matrix

$$Z_{ij} = X_{ij}^* / \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{ij}^*)^2} \quad (6)$$

Table 7. The normalized weighted matrix

Rank	Coach	Coaching	Game	Win	Personal honors	Win%	training method	management	Game style	social influenc	individual quality	social appraisa
1	Eddie Robinson	0.059	0.029	0.01	0.016	0.041	0.022	0.069	0.072	0.032	0.104	0.097
2	Bear Bryant	0.088	0.041	0.012	0.015	0.038	0.023	0.032	0.097	0.023	0.181	0.101
3	Joe Paterno	0.073	0.031	0.01	0.02	0.039	0.021	0.1	0.075	0.035	0.062	0.084
4	Bobby Bowden	0.084	0.036	0.011	0.028	0.04	0.026	0.071	0.087	0.038	0.087	0.1
5	Tom Osborne	0.134	0.056	0.016	0.017	0.035	0.024	0.086	0.073	0.033	0.112	0.106

(3) Determine the positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution.

Positive ideal solution:

$$\begin{aligned} Z^+ &= (Z_{\max 1}, Z_{\max 2}, \dots, Z_{\max n}) \\ &= (0.134, 0.056, 0.016, 0.028, 0.014, \\ &\quad 0.026, 0.100, 0.097, 0.038, 0.181, 0.106) \end{aligned}$$

Negative ideal solution:

$$\begin{aligned} Z^- &= (Z_{\min 1}, Z_{\min 2}, \dots, Z_{\min n}) \\ &= (0.059, 0.029, 0.010, 0.015, 0.035, \\ &\quad 0.021, 0.032, 0.072, 0.023, 0.062, 0.084) \end{aligned}$$

(4) Calculate Euclidean distances to the positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution of evaluation objects.

$$\begin{aligned} D_i^+ &= \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (Z_{ij \max} - Z_{ij})^2} \\ D_i^- &= \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (Z_{ij \min} - Z_{ij})^2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

(5) Calculate of various solutions and the optimal relative close degree

$$L_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^+ + D_i^-} \quad (8)$$

(6) Compare the solutions

L_i value is between 0 and 1, and the closer to 1, the more optimal the solution is. Table 8 shows the new rank for top5 football coaches. We can see from it, the new rank is consistent with the original rankings, so the model of the system can be thought of as a relatively scientific and reliable.

Table 8. The Relative proximity

Coach	D +	D-	Ci	Rank
Eddie Robinson	0.086014	0.126595	0.595436	1
Bear Bryant	0.075666	0.111139	0.594946	2
Joe Paterno	0.112767	0.061012	0.351088	3
Bobby Bowden	0.140306	0.070438	0.334237	4
Tom Osborne	0.119447	0.058166	0.327486	5

6. OPTIMIZATION

As mentioned above, the model we have built can judge a coach with some factors, which means that we can use this model to look for the “best all time college coach”. But there are also some imperfections in our model, in this section we will take some other factors into account to optimize our model. Considering the real situation, we mainly focus on the influence of time line horizon and genders.

6.1. Time Line Horizon

In this subsection, we will talk about the effect of time line horizon and how we build up a more advanced model. We use basketball coaches as an example. To begin with, we select 530 college coaches as representatives and decide to take the Last Year in every coach’s career as the basic element, because the Last Year is broadly representative and could easily label each coach’s years of career. Then, we find the Last Year of the 265th coach was 1990 after we sort these coaches by the year. So the year of 1990 is a watershed. Depending on this, we classify those data into two types, which has a decisive role in the next calculations.

Besides, we must figure out the impact of time line horizon on our main factors. In order to achieve this goal, we use “Excel 2010” to draw pictures as follows. It’s worth noting that we just focus on three factors—win%, win and personal honor, for those three factors are the main effect and they are also very important for us to select the greater coaches in the model we have built.

Figure 9. Statistical Chart of factor win%

Figure 10. Statistical Chart of factor win

Figure 11. Statistical Chart of factor personal honor

From the illustration, we can see that the numbers of win and personal honor are on the up while the w% falls slightly. As the trend of w% is smooth, we hold that our model could work without the impact of time when we consider only w%. So different time line horizon can only influence two parts of our model—win and personal honor.

Considering the slope of each factor, as well as the previous research, finish a formula to make calculation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Aggregate score} &= \text{score} + \sum (1990 - \text{years}) * \text{slope} * \text{weight} \\
 &= \text{score} + \text{add}(\text{win}) + \text{add}(\text{personal honor}) \\
 &= \text{score} + (1990 - \text{years}) * 0.0139 * 0.089 + \\
 &\quad (1990 - \text{years}) * 0.0154 * 0.276
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

The above formula can optimize our model by avoid the effect of different time line horizon.

6.2 Genders

When it comes to the genders, the factors we focus on have a little change, replacing “personal honor” with “coaching time”. This time, we rank all the coaches according to the figures (from big to small) coming from the two new factors, and then draw corresponding graphs with the information of men and women in the same way we used before.

Figure 12. Statistical Chart of factor win

Figure 9. Statistical Chart of factor coaching time

Compare the result of data for women and men, we can easily discover that both the two factors have some differences. So we optimize our model on the basis of “win” and “coaching time”.

According to the graphs, we know that the men’s result is more remarkable than women’s when it comes to the two factors mentioned above, so we finish the formula to make calculation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{aggregate score} &= \text{score} + \sum \text{slope of women's} / \text{slope of mens's} * \text{weight} \\
 &= \text{score} + \text{add}(\text{win}) + \text{add}(\text{coaching time}) \\
 &= \text{score} + (-6.7195) / (-10.756) * 0.089 + \\
 &\quad (-0.2996) / (-0.5420) * 0.0159 \\
 &= \text{score} + 0.56497
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{10}$$

This formula can optimize our model by avoiding the effect of genders.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The integration of AHP, FCE and TOPSIS methodologies is a hybrid application of soft computing techniques. The aim of the hybrid application is to assess the best college coaches and rank them. This work has established the model to determine the best college coaches, which consists of combination of AHP for ranking the coaches preliminarily, FCE for determining the top5 coaches on three kinds of sport, Topsis method to test the accuracy and reasonableness of the model and optimization. Those four parts can screen all the college coaches by four steps. With this model, we come up with a strategy on what will be both the most efficient and accurate way to find the best coaches. The rank is mainly based on statistics of the coaches, as well as their performance in the past and their potential. Then we make a comprehensive assessment. In the following, we list the ultimate top5 coaches on three kinds of sports.

Our future work will focus on refining the model to be more scientific and more believable. Besides, some factors which are neglected in this model can be further studied if there is more information available.

Rank	1	2	3	4	5
Coach	Eddie Robinson	Bear Bryant	Joe Paterno	Bobby Bowden	Tom Osborne
Total Score	88.56	86.84	85.24	73.85	71.77
Coaching time	4.15	2.77	3.35	2.91	1.82
Game	8.31	6.01	7.75	6.85	4.34
Win	24.87	19.69	24.93	21.76	15.54
Personal honors	14.96	16.62	12.00	8.77	14.77
Win%	5.88	6.48	6.22	6.15	6.95
training method	10.92	10.74	11.46	9.48	10.19
management	3.55	7.55	2.45	3.44	2.85
Game style	3.40	2.50	3.25	2.80	3.35
social influence	7.66	10.73	6.96	6.46	7.48
individual quality	2.35	1.35	3.95	2.79	2.17
social appraisal	2.52	2.41	2.92	2.44	2.31

Best all time college football coach

Rank	1	2	3	4	5
Coaches	Mike Krzyzewski	Dean Smith	Bob Knight	John Wooden	Jim Calhoun
Total score	88.24	81.64	81.49	80.26	77.47
Coaching time	3.37	3.11	3.63	2.51	3.46
game	8.31	7.37	8.28	5.38	8.19
win	24.93	22.12	24.85	16.13	24.58
personal honors	15.24	15.24	6.93	16.62	5.54
win%	6.35	6.45	5.87	6.68	5.79
training method	10.92	10.42	11.32	10.70	11.47
management	3.55	3.16	3.54	3.20	3.37
Game style	3.40	3.36	4.08	3.71	4.26
social influence	7.33	6.49	7.43	6.85	7.66
individual quality	2.35	2.09	3.03	2.94	3.56
social appraisal	2.49	1.84	2.53	2.50	2.63

Best all time college basketball coach

Rank	1	2	3	4	5
Coaches	YORK JERRY	Parker Jack	Mason Ron	BERENSON RED	Comley Rick
coaching time	4.15	4.049	3.644	2.935	3.745
game	8.31	7.698	7.195	6.334	7.822
win	24.93	23.917	24.637	20.531	20.877
win%	5.102	5.343	5.784	5.51	4.62
training method	11.065	10.188	10.155	9.862	9.735
management	3.64	3.647	2.949	3.657	3.292
Game style	3.784	3.635	2.904	3.624	3.179
social influence	7.251	6.83	6.693	6.744	6.542
individual quality	2.376	2.272	1.764	2.752	2.185
social appraisal	2.503	2.478	1.71	2.533	2.217

Best all time college hockey coach

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REFERENCES

- [1] Osman Taylan, Abdallah O. Bafail, Reda M.S. Abdulaal, Mohammed R. and Kabli, "Construction projects selection and risk assessment by fuzzy AHP and fuzzy TOPSIS methodologies", *Applied Soft Computing*, Vol, 17, 2014, pp. 105-116.
- [2] Pablo Aragonés-Beltrána, Fidel Chaparro-González, Juan-Pascual Pastor-Ferrandoc, Andrea Pla-Rubioc, "An AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process)/ANP (Analytic Network Process)-based multi-criteria decision approach for the selection of solar-thermal power plant investment projects", *Energy*, Vol.66, 2014, pp. 222-238.
- [3] Xu Shu-bo, APH method, Tian Jing, Tian Jing University, 1988.
- [4] Ren-guang Zuo, Qiu-ming Cheng, Frederik P. Agterberg, "Application of a hybrid method combining multilevel fuzzy comprehensive evaluation with asymmetric fuzzy relation analysis to mapping prospectivity", *Ore Geology Reviews*, vol. 35, 2009, pp. 101-108.
- [5] V.Y.C. Chen, H. P. Lien, C.H. Liu, J.J.H. Liou, G.H. Tzeng, L.S. Yang, Fuzzy MCDM approach for selecting the best environment-watershed plan, *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 11, 2011, pp. 265–275.
- [6] J.W. Wang, C.H. Cheng, H.K. Cheng, Fuzzy hierarchical TOPSIS for supplier selection, *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2009, pp. 377–386.
- [7] Me-ilan Wang. Excellent sports team coaches study assessment index. *Journal of Shanghai Physical Education Institute*, vol. 16, 1992, pp. 41-43
- [8] <http://www.ranker.com/list/best-college-football-coaches-of-all-time-/johnwarner>
- [9] <http://www.sports-reference.com/cbb/coaches/>
- [10] <http://www.collegehockeynews.com/almanac/coachalltime.php>
- [11] <http://sportsillustrated.cnn.com/college-basketball/>

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